

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Stas Gorelik (2026): Review of Pew’s Global Religious Composition dataset (published on Pew Research Center), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/87B09F39-344B-402C-A13A-6B1C3F7E4354>

Abstract

The Pew Research Center’s Global Religious Composition dataset provides a comprehensive, country-level overview of changes in religious affiliation worldwide over a ten-year period, based on estimates for 2010 and 2020. The data cover more than 200 countries and territories and report population shares for major religious groups, including Christians, Muslims, Hindus, Buddhists, Jews, adherents of other religions, and the religiously unaffiliated. The dataset is derived from a large-scale demographic reconstruction effort combining census data, nationally representative surveys, and population registers.

Licensed as Attribution and Share Alike: Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL) (“share-alike”)

Review of Pew's Global Religious Composition dataset

by Stas Gorelik

The Pew Research Center's Global Religious Composition dataset provides a comprehensive, country-level overview of changes in religious affiliation worldwide over a ten-year period, based on estimates for 2010 and 2020. The data cover more than 200 countries and territories and report population shares for major religious groups, including Christians, Muslims, Hindus, Buddhists, Jews, adherents of other religions, and the religiously unaffiliated. The dataset is derived from a large-scale demographic reconstruction effort combining census data, nationally representative surveys, and population registers.

The primary strength of the dataset lies in its global scope and methodological transparency. Importantly for scholars of Eurasian politics and society, the data cover all post-Soviet states, making the dataset directly relevant for research on religion in the former Soviet region.

The data are especially valuable for research on long-term structural change. For scholars of comparative politics, political demography, and international relations, the dataset enables analyses of how shifts in religious composition may intersect with political institutions, conflict dynamics, migration patterns, or regime type at the country level.

At the same time, several limitations should be noted. First, the dataset does not rely on a single unified survey instrument. Instead, Pew aggregates information from a wide range of sources that differ across countries and over time, including censuses, household surveys, and other sources, such as official statistical releases. While Pew applies extensive harmonization and consistency checks, the underlying sources may vary substantially in quality.

These issues may be particularly salient in politically sensitive religious environments, where religious identification may be underreported, misclassified, or deliberately withheld. In authoritarian or semi-authoritarian settings, individuals may be reluctant to disclose religious affiliations that are stigmatized, restricted, or perceived as politically risky.

Second, the dataset is not suitable for subnational or individual-level analysis. Country-level estimates necessarily obscure substantial within-country variation, especially in large, ethnically or religiously diverse states.

Data access: <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/feature/religious-composition-by-country-2010-2020/>.